

The Role of Social Work in HIV/AIDs Care at Art Centres in Punjab

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Abstract

Antiretroviral Therapy (ART) has been central to India's HIV/AIDS response since 2004, with services provided free of cost through government ART Centres. However, clinical intervention alone is insufficient to ensure long-term adherence and patient retention. Social determinants of health such as poverty, education, social exclusion, and stigma continue to affect vulnerable groups including injecting drug users, truckers, migrants, female sex workers, men who have sex with men, and transgender individuals. These groups often face social isolation, limited awareness, and structural barriers that hinder continuity of care. Social work plays a critical role in linking patients to sustained HIV care by addressing these determinants through psychosocial support, counselling, support systems, and advocacy. This study explores the incorporation of social work functions into the roles of ART professionals at a government ART Centre in Punjab. Based on qualitative interviews with outreach workers, counsellors, and PLHIV and supported by analysis of NACO guidelines and patient flowcharts, the research highlights how various professionals including counsellors, care coordinators, nurses, medical officers, outreach workers and pharmacists who are performing responsibilities grounded in social work practice. These include adherence counselling, disclosure support, LFU tracing, community outreach, partner testing coordination and stigma reduction. Although often unnamed, these social work roles are vital to ensuring ART retention.

Keywords

HIV/AIDS, Social Work, ART Centres, LFU, Punjab, Adherence Counselling, Community Outreach, Psychosocial Support.

Introduction

Antiretroviral Therapy (ART) is the core of HIV/AIDS management in India, providing free medicine since 1 April 2004 at ART Centres in India (Rewari et al., 2021). While medical interventions are important, the success of ART programs is deeply rooted in addressing social determinants of health. Social work considers social determinants of health (social status, income, education and social support networks) essential as it heavily influence physical and mental well-being (CASW, n.d.). Social determinants of health refer to the everyday environment that significantly influence their health status and overall quality of life (World Health Organization, 2008). HIV prevalence is heavily concentrated among marginalized groups such as injecting drug users (IDUs), truckers, men who have sex with men (MSM), female sex workers (FSW), transgenders (TG) and migrants (National AIDS Control Organisation, 2023). These groups face stigma, discrimination, social isolation, less awareness and financial issues. Social work serves as critical connectors between clinical care and social realities by focusing on solutions to the problems. Society problems need social work intervention (Petruzzi et al., 2024). Despite the provision of free ART under the National AIDS Control Programme (NACP), retention of patients in ART care remains a major concern. Factors like stigma, addiction relapse, socio-economic marginalization, and lack of psychosocial support contribute to high rates of Lost to Follow-Up patients (National AIDS Control Organisation, 2021). Social work embedded at ART Centres is uniquely positioned to mitigate these challenges through sustained engagement, community outreach, and integrated counselling support. Social work at Antiretroviral Therapy (ART) Centres play a vital role in bridging the gap between clinical care and community-based support. This paper explores the multifaceted functions of social work within ART Centres—ranging from adherence counselling and stigma reduction to community outreach and policy advocacy. Drawing from observations, existing literature and qualitative interview, the study emphasizes the critical role of social work in enhancing ART retention and reducing Loss to Follow-Up (LFU) among People Living with HIV (PLHIV). The paper concludes with recommendations to institutionalize social work interventions for improving HIV care.

Objective of study

To analyse the scope and nature of social work practice at ART Centres.

Review of Literature

Verma (2020) conducted a detailed study at the ART Centre of King George's Medical University, Lucknow, to examine the awareness of HIV/AIDS among youth and to

understand the psychosocial conditions of HIV-positive patients. The research, based on a sample of 211 HIV-positive individuals selected through random sampling, revealed significant gaps in knowledge regarding HIV transmission, prevention, and treatment. Notably, only 16.1% of respondents reported awareness about HIV/AIDS, and awareness about safe sex (21.8%), sexually transmitted diseases (16.59%), and World AIDS Day (12.8%) was also critically low. The study highlighted the vulnerability of youth aged 15–29 years, particularly those from urban slums, low-income households, and migrant backgrounds, who are often exposed to high-risk behaviors and lack proper guidance. Social workers were identified as instrumental in creating awareness, reducing stigma, and providing psychosocial support through community-based interventions, individual and family counselling, and by linking patients with health and social welfare services. The research emphasized that social work practice in HIV care must be responsive to the socio-economic and cultural contexts of youth, especially in high-prevalence settings. While the study provided valuable insights into HIV awareness and the role of professional social workers in an urban ART setting, it did not address issues related to retention in ART, particularly among patients lost to follow-up or among injecting drug users in rural or peri-urban regions. These areas remain underexplored and are the focus of the present research, which seeks to extend the understanding of social work interventions into high-LFU districts of Punjab.

The Canadian Association of Social Workers (CASW) outlines a comprehensive framework for social work practice in HIV/AIDS care, emphasizing the importance of addressing both individual needs and broader structural barriers that affect People Living with HIV (PLHIV). Social workers support clients through counselling, therapy, and psychosocial services, especially in managing issues like disclosure, intimate partner violence, addiction, anxiety, and bereavement (Canadian Association of Social Workers [CASW], n.d.). Additionally, they assist in navigating complex systems such as healthcare, legal aid, income security programs, and housing services. At the community level, social workers play a pivotal role in HIV prevention and harm reduction through public education, advocacy, and program development. They engage in needs assessments, participate in interdisciplinary teams, and coordinate peer and family support groups to build long-term resilience. CASW further emphasizes that healthcare must be understood beyond clinical care, highlighting the need to address stigma, poverty, and social exclusion that disproportionately affect HIV-positive individuals. Although this model is framed within the Canadian healthcare context, its core principles—patient-centred counselling, harm reduction, community outreach, and structural advocacy—are universally applicable, particularly in settings like Punjab, where stigma and economic barriers contribute significantly to poor ART adherence and Lost to Follow-Up (LFU) cases.

Sharma (2025) highlights the critical and evolving role of social workers in responding to the HIV/AIDS epidemic through a multidimensional framework encompassing advocacy, care, and prevention. The study emphasizes that despite advancements in medical treatment, social and psychological barriers—especially stigma and systemic inequities—continue to hinder access to care, particularly among marginalized populations. Social workers play an instrumental role in mitigating these challenges by advocating for equitable health policies, facilitating access to services, and providing targeted psychosocial support. Drawing from a qualitative methodology that included interviews with experienced practitioners and a comprehensive review of literature, the research identifies five key domains of social work intervention: policy advocacy, mental health counselling, stigma reduction, community mobilization, and service integration. Social workers actively participate in public awareness campaigns, offer culturally sensitive educational interventions, and connect individuals to essential services such as ART, housing, and legal aid. Importantly, the study underscores the collaborative nature of social work, where professionals engage with healthcare providers and community organizations to deliver patient-centered and holistic care. While acknowledging these significant contributions, the paper also draws attention to persistent challenges such as heavy caseloads, lack of professional training, and resource constraints in underfunded settings. These findings are especially pertinent to the context of Punjab, where social workers must respond to the dual burden of HIV and substance dependence, address widespread stigma, and improve ART retention among high-risk populations. Sharma's work affirms the transformative potential of social work in the HIV/AIDS response and advocates for sustained policy and institutional support to enhance their impact.

Methodology

This qualitative study is based on:

Primary Data: Semi-structured interview with ART professionals at government ART Centre in Punjab.

Secondary Data: Analysis of patient flowcharts, NACO operational guidelines for ART Services, 2021 (National AIDS Control Organization, 2021).

Analysis

Figure 1: Patient Flow in the ART centre

Source: National Aids Control Organization. (2021). National operational guidelines for ART services, 2021. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. Retrieved from <https://naco.gov.in>

Integration Of Social Work Into The Roles Of Art Professionals In Hiv Care Across Art Centres In Punjab.

The patient flow chart (Figure 1) illustrates that each stage of HIV care starting from pre-ART counselling to adherence during lifelong ART requires more than clinical expertise. It involves active engagement with the patient's psychosocial realities, cultural context and support systems. The following roles while formally attributed to healthcare staff are deeply embedded in social work practice:

1. Care Coordinators

Care coordinators are often the first point of human contact after diagnosis and their initial interaction can significantly shape a patient's engagement with care. Their delivery of peer education and psychosocial support aligns with the social work value of human dignity and the importance of human relationships, as they create a safe and empathetic environment during avulnerable time.

They activate social networks by preparing patients for ART adherence and identifying supportive caregivers, fulfilling the social work principle of strengthening natural support systems. This role also reflects the case management function of social work, where the professional serves as a link between individual needs and community resources.

2. Counsellors

Counsellors provide preparedness counselling which ensure contact information is up to date and assess whether family or partners need to be tested.

Their work in addressing psychosocial barriers, assisting with status disclosure and coordinating referrals to other services directly corresponds to the core competencies of social work: empathy, active listening, crisis intervention and empowerment.

Moreover, they foster a strengths-based approach by promoting positive living and reducing internalized stigma that helps clients cope with chronic illness while maintaining agency and dignity.

3. Staff Nurses

Although clinically trained, staff nurses at ART Centres often take on extended roles, such as educating patients, monitoring adherence, and providing psychosocial encouragement. Their active follow-up in cases of advanced HIV disease touches upon the social work function of continuity of care.

Their screening for co-morbid conditions like TB and non-communicable diseases (NCDs) also requires understanding a patient's socioeconomic situation (housing, nutrition, substance use) which places their intervention in line with social work's person-in-environment perspective.

This dual focus on body and mind reflects an integrated bio-psycho-social model of care which is foundational in social work.

4. Medical Officers

Medical officers are not only responsible for ART initiation but also engage in adherence counselling and readiness assessment, which require understanding patient behaviour, fears, and motivations. These elements are grounded in psychosocial assessment frameworks used by social workers.

They guiding patients through health system navigation from lab tests to support schemes especially to less educated and marginalised.

Their function promotes equity in access, especially for patients from disadvantaged backgrounds who may face systemic or bureaucratic obstacles.

5. Outreach Workers

Outreach workers perform classic field-based social work. Their role in tracing Lost to Follow-Up (LFU) cases include conducting home visits and offering emotional counselling are interventions rooted in community practice and engagement, major domains in social work.

Their sustained efforts to maintain patient communication, provide reassurance and re-engage individuals in care address structural barriers and psychosocial disconnect, especially among patients facing stigma, addiction, or family rejection.

Outreach work reflects a rights-based approach, seeking to reinstate healthcare as a fundamental right and ensuring that the most vulnerable are not excluded.

6. Pharmacists

Though often seen as technical professionals, pharmacists at ART Centres play a subtle yet important role in patient education and emotional reassurance. Their pill adherence counselling and explanation of side effects help reduce anxiety which is essential in long-term ART retention.

These efforts support the patient's self-efficacy which is one of the guiding themes in empowerment-focused social work.

Moreover, patients don't face medicine stockouts or confusion by managing drug registers and ensuring pharmacists help stabilize the treatment environment which is a prerequisite for emotional stability and continuity of care.

These professionals work collaboratively to create a continuum of care model which addresses not only physical treatment but also emotional, social, and educational support for PLHIV—all of which align with the holistic framework of social work.

Application Of Social Work Values In Hiv Care At Art Centres

These values are based on the ethical framework outlined by the National Association of Social Workers (NASW, 2021). They serve as a foundation for assessing how various ART Centre professionals perform roles that align with core social work principles.

Service

The social work value of service emphasizes an unwavering commitment to assisting those in need and responding to social challenges. At ART Centres, this is demonstrated by the dedication of care coordinators, counsellors, and outreach workers who routinely go beyond their formal responsibilities. Whether it involves making repeated visits to the homes of Lost to Follow-Up (LFU) patients, helping bedridden clients access ART, or volunteering time to support women facing abandonment, the spirit of service underpins much of the care work. Professionals often assist with non-clinical needs such as filling out pension forms, facilitating linkages to nutritional aid, or ensuring transport for follow-up care illustrating the centrality of this value in daily practice.

Social Justice

The principle of social justice guides social workers to challenge inequalities and promote equitable access to services, especially for marginalized groups. Within ART Centres, this is seen in targeted support for injecting drug users, migrants, sex workers, and transgender persons which are groups often excluded from mainstream healthcare. Social workers and allied professionals advocate for non-discriminatory treatment policies, organize sensitization sessions for medical staff and intervene when patients face barriers like refusal of services or harassment in public spaces. These actions reflect a broader commitment to dismantling stigma and ensuring that no one is denied care due to social status, identity, or past behaviour.

Dignity and Worth of the Person

Respecting the inherent dignity of each client is central to HIV care. At ART Centres, this value is reflected in the way patients are engaged during counselling, especially during sensitive moments such as HIV status disclosure or treatment initiation. Staff are trained to offer non-judgmental support and involve patients in decisions about their care. Professionals play a crucial role in affirming their right to health and respect in cases involving women who have been abandoned or transgender clients facing institutional hostility. Where needed, they take deliberate steps to ensure privacy such as using discreet methods during follow-ups or offering counselling in protected spaces which help to preserve the person's sense of dignity.

Importance of Human Relationships

The therapeutic alliance between ART staff and patients is often the cornerstone of adherence and continued care. Building trusting human relationships helps clients open about fears, challenges, and support needs. Outreach workers and counsellors often form sustained bonds with PLHIV, allowing them to identify early signs of disengagement or distress. These relationships extend beyond the individual, involving families, caregivers and peer groups to foster collective resilience. ART teams embody this value in both clinic-based and field-level interventions by maintaining supportive contact during relapse or treatment fatigue.

Integrity

Integrity involves honest, ethical and transparent conduct in professional duties. At ART Centres, this value is upheld through accurate recordkeeping, respectful patient interactions, and responsible communication of clinical and psychosocial information. Staff are expected to provide truthful guidance about treatment options, side effects, and long-term care expectations. In particularly sensitive cases, such as domestic violence or substance abuse, professionals must balance openness with discretion, ensuring that patient rights and trust are not compromised. Upholding ethical boundaries is essential to maintaining a credible and compassionate care environment.

Competence

The value of competence requires continuous professional growth and application of relevant knowledge. In the context of ART services, this includes familiarity with evolving HIV treatment protocols, psychosocial counselling strategies, harm reduction approaches and community-specific challenges. Effective practitioners are those who adapt their interventions to the diverse realities of their clients whether it's understanding the social pressures faced by adolescent girls or navigating reintegration for LFU patients returning from prison or rehabilitation. Ongoing training, reflective practice and case-based learning are integral to upholding this value and ensuring responsive, context-aware HIV care.

Conclusion

The social work function at ART Centres in India is deeply embedded within the operational fabric of HIV care delivery, even if not always labelled as such. Through roles such as counsellors, care coordinators, and outreach workers, ART Centres provide critical psychosocial support, enhance treatment adherence, and build community linkages essential for long-term HIV management. The operational guidelines and patient flow mechanisms analysed in this paper underscore the multidimensional nature of ART services—where medical treatment must be integrated with consistent, compassionate, and community-informed social work practice. Recognising and institutionalising these roles can significantly enhance retention outcomes and the holistic wellbeing of PLHIV across India.

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